

ACTIVE DAMPING OF ADAPTIVE COMPOSITE THIN-WALLED BEAMS CONSIDERING THE PRETWIST ANGLES

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SUMMARY: Dynamic response of rotating adaptive composite thin-walled beam with distributed sensors and actuators is studied in this paper. Active damping property of structure is obtained by distributed sensors and actuators which are embedded between composite layers. Variation of active damping performance for the position and the amount of sensor/actuator pair is discussed. Further, performance factors of dynamic characteristics that are the lay-up type, the fiber orientation, setting angle and pretwist angle in host-structure are considered. Finite element method is applied in the numerical study, and negative velocity feedback control algorithm is employed to generate the active damping. The paper continues with an investigation into influences of parameters such as the rotating speed, pretwist angle and the fiber orientation in host structures. Also, it is confirmed that effective damping performance can be obtained through the suitable arrangement and distributed size of sensor and actuator pair using case study.

KEYWORDS: active damping, rotating composite beam, piezo-composite sensor/actuator, velocity feedback control, thin-walled beam, pretwist angle

INTRODUCTION

Thin-walled beams are applied to a lot of fields in aerospace engineering and other industries. Helicopter blades, tilt-rotor aircraft blades, flexible robot arms and wind turbines are representative examples of structures that have the shape of a thin-walled beam. Recently, composite materials have been widely used in structures, obtaining an increased specific stiffness and specific strength. As a result, vibration suppression has arising as an important problem for the operating quality of the system, because composite structures possess flexible characteristics. Vibration suppression methods are classified into passive method and active method. Recently, the later has been focus of research, because it can be allowed the adaptability according to circumstances. Especially, researches have been intensifying over the past two decades regarding active vibration control methods for structures using smart materials. The potential and suitability of using smart composite structures for active suppression of vibration in aerospace industry is a widely investigated topic of research. The most widely used smart materials for vibration control in structures are piezoelectric materials since it has desirable characteristics; fast response and covering a broad range of frequency. They generate an electric charge when subject to a mechanical deformation, which is called the direct piezoelectric effect. Conversely, the mechanical stress or strain is produced by applied electric field, which is called the converse piezoelectric effect. These properties allow piezoelectric materials to act as distributed sensors and actuators in the active control of dynamic systems. There have also been numerous researches regarding a rotating active beam

using piezoelectric materials [1-5].

Until now, the most widely used piezoceramics (such as lead zirconate titanate : PZT) for vibration control are in the form of thin sheet that can be readily embedded or attached to composite structures. However, the typical piezoceramic actuator has some disadvantages. They have the brittle nature of piezoceramics which makes them vulnerable to damage. In addition, they can hardly conform to the curved surface. To overcome these drawbacks of the typical piezoceramic actuator, Active Fiber Composite actuator (AFC) and Macro Fiber Composite actuator (MFC) were developed [6,7]. These piezo-composite materials consist of the piezoceramic fiber, epoxy matrix and interdigitated electrode. In addition, they have advantages as follows. Piezo-composite materials can utilize the d_{11} piezoelectric constant to the direction of piezoceramic fibers which is larger than the d_{31} piezoelectric constant of the typical piezoceramic actuator. Also, the polymer matrix can protect piezoceramic fibers against the impact and it makes piezo-composite materials flexible. Therefore, they can conform to the curved surface easily. These advantages of piezo-composite materials can be applied to more practical applications of smart structure technology. Further, piezocomposite materials can produce a twisting actuation due to the anisotropic characteristics; difficult to achieve using the typical piezoceramic actuator [8-10].

Many researches about the active damping of rotating beams for vibration suppression have used general piezoceramic actuators. Thus the piezo-composite actuators that have many advantages were selected for the vibration suppression of rotating beams in this study. The object of this research is to enhance the damping performance for vibration suppression of the rotating composite thin-walled beam using MFC actuators and PVDF sensors. The formulation is based on single cell composite beam including a warping function, centrifugal force, Coriolis acceleration, pretwist angle and piezoelectric effect. A negative velocity feedback control algorithm coupling the direct and converse piezoelectric effect is used to actively control the dynamic response of a structure through a closed control loop. Numerical study is performed using a finite element method, and dynamic response of the beam is investigated. Newmark time integration method is used to calculate the time response of the model. It is studied that feedback control gain effects on damping performance. Further, influences of parameters such as the rotating speed, the pretwist angle, the setting angle of the beam and the fiber orientation in host structures are investigated. Also, it is confirmed that effective damping performance can be obtained through the suitable arrangement and distributed size of sensor and actuator pair using case study.

FORMULATION

The rotating straight flexible beam in Fig. 1 is considered. The origin of the rotating axis system (X, Y, Z) is located at the root. R_0 is the radius of the hinge that is considered to be rigid in which the beam is mounted. Also, the beam rotates about its polar axis through the origin O . The length of the beam is l and it has the constant rotating speed Ω normal to the plane of rotation. Further, the local coordinate system (X_p, Y_p, Z_p) is considered. Y_p and Z_p are principle axes of an arbitrary beam cross section which is considered about pretwist angle. There are the following transformation formulas between two coordinate systems which are (X, Y, Z) and (X_p, Y_p, Z_p) [11].

$$\begin{Bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \beta(x) & -\sin \beta(x) \\ 0 & \sin \beta(x) & \cos \beta(x) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} X^p \\ Y^p \\ Z^p \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where, $\beta(x) = \gamma + \beta_0 \frac{x}{l}$

In Eq. (1), γ is the setting angle, β_0 is the pretwist angle per unit blade length, and $\beta(x)$ is the pretwist angle in arbitrary section. The fixed coordinate system ($\underline{X}, \underline{Y}, \underline{Z}$) is attached to the center of the hub O . In addition, the local cartesian coordinate system (x, t, n) is located at the mid-plane of the cross-section of the laminate beam wall and moves around the contour with circumferential coordinate s . In the local coordinate system, t is the tangential coordinate and n is the outward normal coordinate.

Also, when basic assumptions in reference [12, 13] are applied, the position, velocity and acceleration vectors for the deformed structure are described as:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\mathbf{R}} &= (x+u+R_0)\mathbf{i} + (y+v)\mathbf{j} + (z+w)\mathbf{k} \\ \bar{\mathbf{v}} &= (\dot{u}-\Omega(y+v))\mathbf{i} + (\dot{v}+\Omega(x+u+R_0))\mathbf{j} + \dot{w}\mathbf{k} \\ \bar{\mathbf{a}} &= (\ddot{u}-2\Omega\dot{v}-\Omega^2(x+u+R_0))\mathbf{i} + (\ddot{v}+2\Omega\dot{u}-\Omega^2(y+v))\mathbf{j} + \ddot{w}\mathbf{k}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

Further, constitutive equations including piezoelectric effect in plane stress problem can be written as,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{ss} \\ \tau_{xs} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{ss} \\ \gamma_{xs} \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_{nxx} \\ \bar{e}_{nss} \\ \bar{e}_{nxs} \end{bmatrix} E_n \quad \text{where, } E_n = -\frac{V}{e_s}\quad (3)$$

In Eq.(3), \bar{e}_n is transformed piezoelectric stress constant, E_n is electric field, V is applied voltage and e_s is electrode space.

Then, the strain energy and the kinetic energy of the beam can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned}U &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_{\Gamma} (N_{xx} \delta \epsilon_{xx}^0 + N_{xs} \delta \gamma_{xs} + M_{xx} \delta \kappa_{xx}) ds dx + U_{CF} \\ T &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_{\Gamma} \int_h \rho v \cdot v dndsdx\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where, U_{CF} is the strain energy due to the centrifugal force.

To derive the governing equation of motion, Hamilton's principle is applied.

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{C}_C\dot{\mathbf{q}}(\mathbf{t}) + (\mathbf{K}_L + \mathbf{K}_{CF} + \mathbf{K}_R)\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{F}_v + \mathbf{F}_{CF} + \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{t})\quad (5)$$

where, \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C}_C , \mathbf{K}_L , \mathbf{K}_{CF} , \mathbf{K}_G , \mathbf{F}_{CF} and $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{t})$ are the mass matrix, the Coriolis matrix, the linear stiffness matrix, the stiffness matrix due to centrifugal force, the geometric stiffness matrix, centrifugal force vector and arbitrary exited load, respectively.

Further, electric force vector, \mathbf{F}_v can be written as

$$\mathbf{F}_v = \int_L \int_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{HN})^T \mathbf{PE} ds dx = \mathbf{K}_{av} V_a\quad (6)$$

From direct piezoelectric effect, sensor equation can be derived. Sensors are thin film-shape materials such as PVDF. Also, since no external electric field is applied to the sensor layer, and as the charge is collected only in the thickness direction in PVDF sensor, only the electric displacement D_3 is of interest [1,3]. As geometric condition that the width of panel is relatively smaller than the length of the panel, the electric displacement of sensor layer can be derived as,

$$D_3 = e_{31} \epsilon_{xx} = e_{31} (U_{,x} - Y \beta_{z,x} + Z \beta_{y,x} + \psi \phi_{,xx})\quad (7)$$

The total charge generated on the sensor surface is the spatial summation of all the point charge on the sensor layer. Therefore, the current on the surface of a sensor can be presented as

$$i(t) = \frac{dq_s(t)}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \int_A D_3 dA \right)\quad (8)$$

When the piezoelectric sensors are used as strain rate sensors, the current can be converted into the open circuit sensor voltage output V_s as,

$$V_s = G_c i(t) = G_c \frac{dq_s(t)}{dt} \quad (9)$$

where G_c is the gain of the current amplifier transforming the sensor current voltage.

The distributed sensor generate a voltage when the structures is oscillating and this signal is fed back into the distributed actuator using a control algorithm.

The system actuating voltage can be presented as,

$$V_a = G_c G_i \mathbf{K}_{sv} \dot{\mathbf{q}} \quad (10)$$

In the feedback control, the electric force vector \mathbf{F}_v can be regarded as a feedback force.

$$\mathbf{F}_v = \mathbf{K}_{av} G_c G_i \mathbf{K}_{sv} \dot{\mathbf{q}} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Let } \mathbf{C}_v = -\mathbf{K}_{av} G_c G_i \mathbf{K}_{sv} \quad (12)$$

Then, the governing equation considering velocity feedback control becomes

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(\mathbf{t}) + (\mathbf{C}_c + \mathbf{C}_v)\dot{\mathbf{q}}(\mathbf{t}) + (\mathbf{K}_L + \mathbf{K}_{CF} + \mathbf{K}_R)\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{F}_{CF} + \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{t}) \quad (13)$$

As shown in this equation, the voltage control algorithm has a damping effect on the vibration suppression of a distributed system. Also, the time response of system is obtained through Newmark time integration method.

NUMERICAL RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Code Verifications

To verify the code for numerical simulation, the natural frequency of the rotating composite box beam is compared with the previous data. Stacking sequence of the model is $[-30]_6$ in top, $[30]_6$ in bottom, $[30/-30]_3$ in right and left panel, respectively. Table.1 shows the lowest three natural frequencies for the rotating speed of 1014 rpm. There are good agreement between present results and reference [14-16]. Also, the actuating performance of piezo-composite materials is examined. The model verified is the single-cell beam with the cross-section of NACA0012 airfoil. Further, the AFC packs are embedded between glass-epoxy layers as active materials [8]. Fig.2 shows the twist angle at the tip of the active beam under various applied voltages and the present results are almost equal to the data in reference.

Table 1. Natural frequency (Hz) of symmetric lay-up box beam

Mode	Experiment [14] Chandra & Chopra	Analysis [15] Smith & Chopra	Analysis [16] Stemple & Lee	Present
Flap1	28.60	28.13	27.33	27.65
Lag1	39.5	42.85	38.66	42.16
Flap2	135.0	139.8	133.6	135.7

Vibration Suppression through a Negative Velocity Feedback Control

To investigate the active damping effect through a velocity feedback control algorithm with distributed piezoelectric sensors and actuators, a rotating composite thin-walled beam as shown in Fig. 1 is considered. Dimensions of length, width, height and hinge offset are 844.5mm, 23.1mm, 12.6mm and 10% of the span, respectively. Host structures are graphite-epoxy, while sensors and actuators are PVDF having a thin film shape and MFC that is piezo-composite materials, respectively. Sensors and actuators are embedded between composite layers at center of the cross-section. Further, MFC actuators are laminated at 0 degree with respect to beam axis for bending control. Stacking sequence of host structures is $[-30]_6$ in top, $[30]_6$ in bottom, $[30/-30]_3$ in right and left panel, respectively. Fig. 3 shows the time response of the beam under an impulsive load to Z-axis when it rotates with 0 rpm. The beam is oscillated to flapping direction by an impulse load. Also, because the beam has elastic coupling effects for flap-lag and bending-torsion in symmetric lay-up, lagging and torsional oscillations are generated. Fig. 3 presents that the oscillation in the three directions can be damped out using a negative feedback control algorithm. As control gain is increased, damping effect is higher and vibrations are decreased quicker. Fig. 4 shows the variation of the damping ratio at the 1st flap and lag mode for increasing of feedback control gain. The damping ratio increases constantly as the feedback control gain increases. But, feedback control gain can not be increased infinitely because applied voltage must be limited for the sake of breakdown voltage of actuators.

Fig. 3. Time response of symmetric lay-up beam subject to an impulsive load

Fig. 4. The variation of damping ratio for various feedback control gains

(a) Frequency

(b) Damping ratio

Fig. 5. The variation for the change of rotating speed

Fig. 6. The effect of pretwist angle per unit length of the blade at 1000 rpm

Fig. 7. The effect of setting angle at 1000 rpm

Effects of Rotating Speed and Pretwisted Angle

Generally, rotating beams like rotor blades, have specific rotating speed for operation. This operating speed is varies with the type of system and operating status. Also, most of blades have pretwist angle and it is common design factor for blades. Thus the damping effect needs to be investigated for each variation of the rotating speed and pretwist angle. Above all, the effect of rotating speed is discussed. The symmetric lay-up beam which is used in last discursion is considered for numerical simulation. Fig. 5 shows the variation of frequencies and damping ratios at the 1st and 2nd modes when the same feedback control gain ($G_i = 3000$) is applied. Frequencies increase as the rotating speed is increased, due to a larger centrifugal force at higher rpm. Conversely, the damping ratio decreases at higher rpm when the frequency increases.

Secondly, the effect of the pretwist angle is presented. The pretwist angle is constituted with components that are the pretwist angle per unit length and setting angle of the beam as shown in Fig. 1. Firstly, three anti-symmetric lay-up beams are considered to investigate the effect of pretwist angle per unit length of the beam (β_0). Their stacking sequence of host structures are $[0\ 15\ 0\ 15\ 0\ 15]_r$, $[0\ 30\ 0\ 30\ 0\ 30]_r$ and $[0\ 45\ 0\ 45\ 0\ 45]_r$, respectively. Further, sensors and actuators are embedded between composite layers at center of the cross-section. When the same feedback control gain ($G_i = 3000$), setting angle ($\gamma = 0$), and rotating speed (1000rpm) are applied, Fig. 6 shows the effect of pretwist angle of the beam for frequencies and damping ratios at the 1st and 2nd mode. As shown in Fig. 6, frequencies decrease and damping ratios increase as pretwist angle per unit length of the beam is to be larger. Also, the effect of setting angle is investigated, too. Beams that have stacking sequence in host structures $[-\theta]_6$ in top, $[\theta]_6$ in bottom, $[\theta/-\theta]_3$ in right and left panel is considered. Active layers are located at the center of the wall. When same control gain ($G_i = 3000$), pretwist angle per unit length of the

beam ($\beta_0 = 0$) and rotating speed ($1000rpm$) are applied, Fig. 7 shows the effect of setting angle of the blade. As the setting angle is to be larger, the frequency of the 1st flap mode decreases and the frequency of the 1st lag mode increases. On the other hand, the damping ratio of the 1st flap mode is increased and the damping ratio of the 1st lag mode is decreased. In general actual blade, the pretwist angle is not moderately large. So, variation of damping effect that is induced by pretwist angle is smaller than other factors.

The Effect of Ply-angle in Host Structures

Fiber orientation of composite materials is a very important design factor for composite thin-walled beams. Generally, the variation of the ply-angle in host structures effects on the frequency, while the change of frequency influences to the damping effect that is obtained through a negative velocity control. First of all, three cases of beam each possessing a different lay-up type are considered. Case 1 ($[0\theta 0\theta 0\theta]$) and Case 2 ($[\theta]_6$) are anti-symmetric lay-up beam and Case 3 ($[-\theta]_6$ top, $[\theta]_6$ bottom, $[\theta/-\theta]_3$ right&left) is a symmetric lay-up beam. When the same control gain ($G_i = 3000$) and rotating speed ($500rpm$) are applied, Fig. 8 shows the influence of the change of ply-angle in the host structures. As the ply-angle in host structures decreases, frequencies of the beam increase, while damping ratios decrease as shown in Figs. 8 (a) and (b). This result is induced because the bending stiffness of beams becomes larger at a smaller ply-angle in host structures. Also, Fig. 8 (c) shows the case that the damping ratio are considered with the frequency. The absolute damping effect is the highest when beams have the fiber-orientation with 30deg. Further, in these cases, it is confirmed that the symmetric lay-up beam has a higher damping performance than the anti-symmetric lay-up beam. From these results, the frequency and damping ratio have a converse relation. So, if the frequency is increased, the damping effect is decreased. Further, the damping performance can be increased through the proper structural tailoring of composite materials that are passive structures.

(a) Frequency

(b) Damping ratio

(c) Real part of eigenvalue
(the absolute value)

Fig. 8. The effect of ply-angle in host structures at various rotating speed

The Influence of the Position and Area of Sensor/Actuator Pair

The position and area of the sensor/actuator pair are important factors for effective vibration reduction in an active beam. Due to the high cost of piezoelectric sensors and actuator, suitable arrangements for position and the distributed area of sensor/actuator pair need to be discussed for economical use of active materials.

Initially, the beam with $1000rpm$ has a symmetric lay-up and the stacking sequences in host structure are $[-\theta]_6$ in top, $[\theta]_6$ in bottom, $[\theta/-\theta]_3$ in right and left panel, respectively. Also, sensor/actuator pair of which size is 5% of total surface area of the thin-walled beam is considered. When the position of sensor/actuator pair is changed from root to tip of the beam, damping ratios of the 1st flap and lag mode are calculated in Fig. 9 (a). Damping effect is the

highest when sensor/actuator pair is located near the root of the beam. But, as the position of sensor/actuator pair is moved to the tip, the damping performance is decreased dramatically. Besides, when the sensor/actuator pair is located over than about 80% of beam span from the root, the damping effect is nearly zero. Because the 1st flap and lag modes are the most important mode to bending control of the beam, the sensor/actuator near the root offer better vibration suppression. Also, the sensor/actuator pair near the tip of beam is invalid as active structure. Further, Fig. 9 (b) shows the damping ratios of the 2nd flap and lag mode. Damping ratio is larger than another position when sensor/actuator pair is located near the root and about 50% span. But, the contribution of the 1st modes is very larger than another higher mode in the case of the slender beam. Therefore, the root of beam is more effective than if it where in other location for sensor/actuator position.

Secondly, the symmetric lay-up beam in is considered to discuss the influence of the distributed area of the sensor/actuator pair. And, the effect of the change of the active area is calculated in non-rotating condition. When the area of the sensor/actuator pair increases from 5% to 100% of the total surface area, damping ratios usually increase. But, as the active area is increased to over about 80% of the total surface area, the damping ratio is decreased slightly as shown in Fig. 10 (b). This was due to the sensor/actuator pairs near the tip being invalid as an active structure and they only act like added mass at the tip. Therefore, actuators near the tip of the beam (about 80~100% of span) have a negative effect on the damping performance. In addition, as the area of sensor/actuator pair is changed, frequencies are changed, as shown in Fig. 10 (a). As the decreasing of the frequency in structures need to be eluded generally, suitable active area for considering the 1st flap and lag mode is approximately 70% of the total surface area as shown in Fig. 10 (c).

Generally, the cost of active materials is high with the mass of the system increasing as more actuator is used. So, adequate vibration suppression performance will be obtained through the proper arrangement and distributed size of sensor/actuator pair.

(a) The 1st flap & lag mode

(b) The 2nd flap & lag mode

Fig. 9. The variation of damping ratio for the position of sensor and actuator pair

(a) The variation of frequencies

(b) The variation of damping ratios

(c) The variation of real parts of eigenvalue (the absolute value)

Fig. 10. Influence of the active area

CONCLUSIONS

Vibration suppression of rotating composite thin-walled beam with MFC actuators and PVDF sensors is studied. The results in this study illustrate that an active damping effect can be obtained through negative velocity feedback control algorithm with PVDF sensors and MFC actuators. The active damping effect has linear relation for feedback control gain, so vibrations can be damped out quicker when the higher feedback control gain is applied within the limit of actuator voltage. Further, the rotating speed, the pretwist angle, the setting angle, fiber-orientation of composite materials, the position and distributed area of sensor/actuator have an effect on the active damping performance. Accordingly, adequate vibration suppression performance will be obtained through the suitable arrangement and distributed size of sensor/actuator pair. Also, it is confirmed that the optimal design and the optimal control theory need to be studied for obtaining the optimal damping effect of rotating composite thin-walled beam. This research with PVDF sensors and MFC actuators can apply to enhance the damping performance for vibration suppression of helicopter blades, tilt-rotor aircraft blades, flexible robot arms and wind turbine, etc.

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